

MECHANICAL DIRECT JOINING BETWEEN CFRTP AND METAL SHEET USING HIGH FREQUENCY INDUCTION HEATING

Kaname.FUJIFAKU¹, Kou.KUWABARA², Toshiyuki.YASUHARA³

¹ Department of Environmental Symbiotic System, Nippon Institute of Technology
 Miyashiro-machi, Minamisaitama-gun, Saitama Pref, 345-8501, Japan

E-mail: 2186003@sstu.nit.ac.jp

² Calsonic Kansei Corporation

2-1917 Nisshin-cho, Kita-ku, Saitama City, Saitama

E-mail: 1fuji2taka3nasuvi@gmail.com

³ Department of Robotics, Nippon Institute of Technology

Miyashiro-machi, Minamisaitama-gun, Saitama Pref, 345-8501, Japan

E-mail: yasut@nit.ac.jp

Keywords: CFRTP, Mechanical Joining, High Frequency Induction Heating

ABSTRACT

Nowadays lightweight materials such as aluminum alloy or magnesium alloy, also High Tensile Strength Steel have been used for weight reduction of motor vehicles. Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRPs) have been also used for weight reduction because it have remarkable high specific strength. However they have been only adopted airplane or parts of high grade cars due to its cost. In these days, problems concerning of CFRP's applications for motor vehicles have decreased by various researches, multi material include CFRP could be used on motor vehicle designs. Generally it is still difficult to join different materials. Though there are a lot of reports about joining between CFRP and metals ^[1-2], the joining strength depends on the strength of rivets or the matrix material of CFRP. In this study, joining method between aluminum sheet and CFRTP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermo-Plastic) sheet without rivets by using induction heating was discussed, and joining strength were investigated. In this paper, joining strength was evaluated for different direction from conventional direction. Also, optimization of joining condition was performed to reduce time taken for joining. From the result of experimental, optimal joining condition in this method was determined that load of 200 N was applied up to 1000 N. In this case, joining time was 250 s. Also, joining strength of side direction was assumed that it affected by tensile and shear. Prediction formula of joining strength of side direction was determined with considering strength of base metal and layout.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays various efforts has made to countermeasure global warming. Among them, reduction of vehicle weight has actively preformed against environmental protection. Lightweight materials such as aluminum alloys and magnesium alloy, also high tensile strength steel have been used for weight reduction of vehicle. Also, carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) has been attracted as a new lightweight material because it have high strength and lightweight characteristic. But it is difficult to make whole parts of products by CFRP, several materials are generally used for motor vehicles. Joining method for different materials is usually using rivets or adhesion bond. In case of joining method between CFRPs and metals, a lot of problems occur. Prepared holes for rivet make the strength weak because they should become starting point of crack due to the break of carbon fiber. The other hand, because adhesion bond joins interface between metal and matrix polymer of CFRP, the joining strength is almost same as the strength of matrix polymer ^[3]. In this study, joining method between aluminum sheet and CFRTP sheet without rivet or adhesion bond are discussed. We have already evaluated that joining strength for one direction in this joining method. And joining strength was able to express by formula with anchor's layout, anchor's angle θ , tensile strength of base metal as parameters ^[4].

In this paper, joining strength was discussed investigate for different direction compared with conventional direction. Also, optimization of joining condition was performed to reduce time taken for joining.

2 JOINING METHOD

2.1 Materials

In this study, CFRTP sheet which matrix was Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) and aluminum sheet (A5052) were joined. CFRTP sheet which was a length of 30 mm, a width of 20 mm, and a thickness of 0.5 mm was stacked on 5 layers. Molding temperature of PMMA is generally about 150 ~ 250 degree C. Characteristic of CFRTP were shown in the Table 1.

Al sheet which was a length of 30 mm, a width of 20 mm and a thickness of 0.5 mm was processed like a grater as shown in Fig.1. Die and punch as shown in Fig.2 was used for processing of anchors. The projection shape was about 1mm squared. Overview of anchor size was shown in Fig.3.

<i>MITSUBISHI RAYON CO.,LTD. Pyrofil™ TR6110</i>	
Matrix	Polymethyl methacrylate
Molding temperature	150 ~ 250 degree C
Filler	PAN based carbon fiber
Fiber filling rate	55 wt%
Thickness	0.5 mm
Number of fiber bundles	6000

Table 1: Characteristic of CFRTP.

Figure 1. Anchors of aluminum plate fabricated by iron punch.

Figure 2. General view of anchors processing apparatus.

Figure 3. Overview of processed anchor.

2.2 Joining procedure

In this study, a high frequency induction heating was used as heating device. The inner diameter of coil was 50mm, and frequency of electrical power supply was set to 60 kHz. Joining apparatus as shown in Fig.4 was used for joining of this study. Die set was used for joining and coil of high frequency induction heating apparatus was installed to center part of die set. Load cell and vacuum chuck made of porous ceramics was installed to upper part of die set and stand made of machinable ceramics was installed to under part of die set. CFRTP sheet was kept by porous ceramic connected to

rotary vacuum pump. A hole of 1 mm - diameter for passing a thermocouple was processed center of machinable ceramics to measure temperature of Al. T type thermo couple of 0.1 mm- diameter was installed through the hole and temperature of Al was measured. Joining was performed by lowering upper part. Joining process was as follow. Al anchor was put to ceramics stand. Al anchor was heated up to about 200 degree C by high frequency induction heating. In the case that, voltage of power supply was set to 30 V. CFRTP was indirectly heated up by contacting Al that has reached 200 degree C. Finally, joining was made progress by applying stepwise load as shown in Fig.5. Temperature of CFRTP sheet gradually rose from nearest layer the Al by contact with Al. Only layer nearest the Aluminum was exceeded to molding temperature. However, it is presumed that molding temperature was exceeded around sticking anchor. CFRTP was little heated by high frequency induction heating when voltage of power supply was 30 V.

Joining process was divided into heating, pressurization and cooling. It totally takes about 250 s for joining. It takes about 180 s for heating and cooling. Over 70% was accounted for heating and cooling time. Reduction of heating and cooling time is needed for shortening of entire joining time.

Figure 4. Joining apparatus.

Figure 5. Joining condition of this joining method.

3 OPTIMIZATION OF JOINING CONDITION

3.1 Parameter of joining condition

High frequency induction heating has characteristics of mold less, non-contact heating and high speed heating. Therefore, this joining method is able to expect high speed joining.

Previous studies have shown that this joining method is sufficiently joined with a joining load of 1000 N^[4]. In this section, joining speed and joining strength were evaluated by change the joining conditions.

Evaluation of joining condition was performed for amount of split load of 50, 100, 200 and 500 N up to 1000N and observation of cross sectional area was performed,

In this experiment, pressure applying time was only discussed. Therefore, in addition to pressurization time, heating time about 60 s and cooling time 90 s are included.

3.2 Result of optimization of joining condition

Result of pressure applying time of each joining condition was shown in Fig.6. In case that load of 500 N was applied up to 1000 N, pressure applying time was 40 s. Split load of 500 N was about 1/6 as small as load division of 50 N. In case of split load of 500 N, total joining time was about 200 s by adding heating time and cooling time.

Maximum test force of each pressurization time was shown in Fig.7. In case of split load 50, 100 and 200 N, maximum test force of all specimens was about 1200 N, variance of test force was smaller than split load 500 N.

When load of 500 N was applied up to 1000 N, variation in maximum test force after tensile test was large and maximum test force was decreased to 75% of maximum value. For the above reasons, this joining method is presumed that joining defects occur by increasing the load applied at one time.

Cause of joining defects was clarified by observed cross section of joining interface. Result of observed cross section of joining interface was shown in Fig.8.

Effect of joining condition such as deformation of Al anchor was not confirmed. In case of load division 50, 100 and 200 N, joining interface of CFRTP side was confirmed that Carbon fiber in CFRTP was fitted along Al anchors. However, when split load 500 N, it was confirmed that carbon fiber in CFRTP was broken by Al anchor. Joining defects occur by broken carbon fiber when over load applied at one time. Cause of joining defects is assumed that matrix of CFRTP (PMMA) was not reached to softening point. Then, joining strength was decreased by decline of hold force to Al anchor.

Therefore, optimal joining condition in this method was determined to load division 200 N. In this case, joining time was 250 s.

Figure 6: Difference of pressurization time on each stepwise load

Figure 7: Maximum test force of each stepwise load

Figure 8: Cross section of joining interface

4 EVALUATION OF JOININGSTRENGTH

4.1 Tensile shear test of the case of side direction

When the test force applied at the front of anchor as shown in Fig.9 (a), investigations of the joining strength have already been done^[4]. In this study, joining strength applied from side direction as shown in Fig.9 (b) was evaluated. This joining method is assumed that it has anisotropy of joining strength because shape of anchor was different by anchor's direction.

Tensile shear test was performed to investigate the joining strength in side direction. In this time, anchor's angle θ was 60 degrees and 90 degrees.

Figure 9: Load receiving face of anchor

4.2 Result of tensile shear test

In case of $\theta = 60$ degrees and side direction, maximum test force was close to value of $\theta = 90$ degrees and conventional direction. However shape of test force – stroke curve was different as shown in Fig.10.

Actually, Shape of specimen after the tensile shear test confirmed 2 pattern deformations as shown in Fig.11 (b). One is larger anchor's deformation in the front line for tensile direction. The other is anchor's angle θ approaching a right angle by anchor's deformation.

Figure 10: Comparison of conventional direction and side direction

(a) Before tensile shear test

(b) After tensile shear test

Figure 11: Shape of specimen from tensile shear test

Effect of these deformations was investigated by changing number of anchor n of one line to 1~5.

Fracture surface of each anchor number n was shown in Fig.12.

In case of $n = 1$, specimen was broken at root of anchor. In case of $n = 2\sim 5$, anchor was damaged like that root of anchor teared up.

Maximum test force of each anchor's number n was shown in Fig.13. .

In case of $n = 1$, maximum test force was about 120 N which is equal to strength of single anchor. Strength of single anchor was determined by cross sectional area of anchor's root and tensile strength of base metal (Tensile strength of A5052 was about 220 MPa) and area of anchor's root is 0.5 mm^2 . When number of anchor was 1, joining strength was only affected by tensile strength which was higher than shear strength because anchor was able to freely rotate and deform by tensile load. Phenomenon was observed only in the case of $n=1$. In case of $n = 2\sim 5$, maximum test force was increased strength of single anchor + $0.5n \times$ strength of single anchor. Joining strength of side direction was presumed that it was affected by shear strain for the reason of increasing tendency of maximum test force and deformation of anchor's root because joining strength was supposed that it was increased by 2 times of single anchor in case of effect of only tensile strength. Therefore, joining strength was evaluated by formula (1).

Formula (1) is relational expression of tensile strength and shear strength that is obtained from von Mises yield criterion. Formula (1) was transformed as to formula (2) and compared of experimental value and calculated value obtained from formula (2). Comparison of experimental value and calculated value was shown in Fig.14. Calculated value of $n = 1$ was applied strength of single anchor because deformation of anchor's root was different to $n = 2\sim 5$.

Increasing tendency of calculated value was similar to experimental value but constant difference appears. Joining strength was assumed that it was affected by both tensile and shear stress. Accordingly, rate of shear strain was determined by experimental value and calculated value as shown in Table 2. Percentage of shear was increased by increasing anchor number of one line.

Figure 12: Fracture surface of each number of anchor n

Figure 13: Maximum test force of each number of anchor n

$$s_{al}/\sqrt{3}=t_{al} \quad (1)$$

$$t_{al} = (s_{al} \times n)/\sqrt{3} \quad (2)$$

s_{al} : Strength of single anchor (N)

t_{al} : Shear strength of single anchor (N)

n : anchor number of one line

Figure 14: Comparison of experimental value and calculated value

Anchor number n of one line	1	2	3	4	5
Shear percentage (%)	0	70	75	80	85

Table 2: Percentage of shear stress

Prediction formula (3) in joining strength of sideway was obtained by applying shear percentage to formula (2). Prediction value was able to approximate for experimental value as shown in Fig.15. It was found that strength of side direction was affected by both tensile strength and shear strength.

$$S = (s_{al} \times n) / (\sqrt{3} \times Ps) \quad (3)$$

S : joining strength (N)
 s_{al} : Strength of single anchor (N)
 n : Anchor number of one line
 Ps : Shear percentage

Figure 15: Comparison of experimental value and prediction value

5 CONCLUSION

Mechanical joining between CFRTP and aluminum sheet were carried out. Shortening of joining time was performed by changing joining condition. Joining process was divided into heating, pressurization and cooling. Pressure applying time and applying load was affected to joining strength.

From the result of Shortening of joining time, optimal joining condition in this method was determined to pressure per time 200 N to avoid the break of CF. in this case, joining time was 250 s. When setting the load applied at one time to 200 N over, joining defects occur.

This joining method is assumed that it has anisotropy of joining strength because shape of anchor was different by anchor's direction. Tensile shear test was performed by side direction. From the result of tensile shear test, root of Al anchor was affected by shear deformation and joining strength of side direction was mixed by tensile and shear stress. For the above reasons, joining strength of side direction was assumed that it expressed by formula (3).

As for the joining strength of side direction, detailed investigation of the all anchor's layout is necessary.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Thanks to lab's member for helping the preparation of the experiment and the production of specimen.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Tetsuya : Japan Welding Society 70(2), 262-265, 2001-03-15
- [2] Y. Yasuhiro : Japan Welding Society 65(6), 463-468, 1996
- [3] K.Ramani and B.Moriarty: Polymer Engineering and Science, 38, 5,870-877, 1998
- [4] K.Kuwabara and T.Yasuhara: Proceeding of ICCM21, 3924, 2018